

Analysis of English Language Research on the Subject "The Role and Role of Local Ruler in the Struggle against Arab Caliphate Coination in VII-VIII Centuries"

Boymirzayev Ismoiljon Khasanovich

History teacher, Fergana State University academic lyceum

Abstract: This article presents some opinions and analyzes about the scientific literature created in English, dedicated to the history of national leaders who fought against the occupation of the Arab caliphate. Including I. Christopher Beckwith, A. R. Gibb, R. N. Fry, S. Whiting Marvin, G. R. Hawting, W. L. Novak, M. D. Luse, P. B. Golden, Sharon Moshe, D. Elton, A. H. Jangebe, B. Hoberman, G. R. Hoyland, B. Jonathan, The contents of Hugh Kennedy's works and their notable ideas are presented.

Keywords: I. Christopher Beckwith, A. R. Gibb, R. N. Fry, S. Whiting Marvin, G. R. Hawting, W. L. Novak, M. D. Luse, P. B. Golden, Sharon Moshe, D. Elton, A. H. Jangebe, B. Hoberman, G. R. Hoyland, B. Jonathan, Hugh Kennedy.

Introduction. Evaluating the activities of historical figures requires an impartial approach to the period in which they lived, political conditions, and social realities. This serves to form the right opinion in the public about that person.

Studying the figures who left a worthy mark in our history contributes to the understanding of the identity of our nation with a rich historical heritage.

Although the realities from ancient times to today are finding their place in scientific literature, artistic works and even textbooks, there is still a lot of work to be done. In particular, it is important for us today to shed light on the life and activities of historical figures, evaluate their place in historical processes, study their achievements and draw conclusions from their shortcomings.

The direct participants in the events related to the Arab invasion that took place in this period: the ikhshids of Sughd (Tarhun, Gurak, Panj governor Devashtich), the gods of Bukhara (Bidun, Qabaj-Khotun, Tughshoda), Nasaf and Kesh (Vik, Ashkand, Ikhrid, Taran), Choch (Bahadur tudun, Inay tudun), Ustrushona (Satachari II, Satachari III, Karabuga, Khanqora) or Fergana rulers (Alutar, Arslan Tarkhan) are still enough. we have no imagination. Currently, it is necessary to determine the historical place of these persons, to show their status both scientifically and ideologically.

Methods: Until now, significant scientific works have been created in world historiography and in our country on the history of Central Asia. In these studies, there are serious comments about some aspects of the history of Central Asia. It is appropriate to divide them geographically and chronologically into 3 groups: 1) literature published in foreign countries; 2) scientific works

created during the Russian Empire and the Soviet era; 3) studies published during the years of independence.

Some information about the history of Central Asia, written by scientists from different countries, can be found [1-19]. Special opinions and comments were not expressed in the studies created in foreign countries regarding the history of the early medieval period of Central Asia. Nevertheless, in the scientific works published in France, Russia, Europe, America, Turkey, China and the countries of Central Asia, some noteworthy points within the framework of the problem of our interest are stated.

English-language studies have a special place in the study of the history of the early medieval period of Central Asia. In English I. Christopher Beckwith, A. R. Gibb, R. N. Fry, S. Whiting Marvin, G. R. Hawting, W. L. Novak, M. D. Luse, P. B. Golden, Sharon Moshe, D. Elton, A. H. Jangebe B. Hoberman, G. R. Hoyland, B. Jonathan and Researchers such as Hugh Kennedy have conducted research [15-16, 20-30].

Results and Discussion: O'rta Osiyoning ilk o'rta asrlar davri tarixini o'rganishda Amerikalik olim I. Kristofer Bekvitning asarlari alohida o'rin tutadi. Uning ijodi "The Tibetan Empire in Central Asia", "Medieval Tibeto-Burman Languages", "Koguryo, the Language of Japan's Continental Relatives", "Phoronyms: Classifiers, Class Nouns, and the Pseudopartitive Construction", "Warriors of the Cloisters: The Central Asian Origins of Science in the Medieval World", "Empires of the Silk Road: A History of Central Eurasia from the Bronze Age to the Present", "Greek Buddha: Pyrrho's Encounter with Early Buddhism in Central Asia" asarlaridan iborat.

Being a linguist, I. Christopher Beckwith mastered Arabic-Persian, Chinese, Japanese and Indian languages well. It is this situation that ensures the high scientific value of his works. The scientist wrote his works "The Tibetan empire in Central Asia: a history of the struggle for great power among Tibetans, Turks, Arabs and Chinese during three early middle ages" and "Empires of the Silk Road (a history of Central Eurasia from the Bronze age to the present)" uses Arabic-Persian and Chinese sources as well as Tibetan documents [15–16].

I. Christopher Beckwith's "The Tibetan empire in Central Asia: a history of the struggle for great power among Tibetans, Turks, Arabs and Chinese during early middle ages" published in 1993 [15: 281] also tells about Ferghana's relations with China during the period of the Turks and Arabs. It contains information about the "Battle of Aksuv" between the Tang Empire and the Arab Caliphate, which took place in the region of Aksuv (Aksu) in August 717 as a result of the Fergana conflict [15: 88-89-p]. The reliability of the information provided by the author is very high, as he effectively used Arabic and Chinese sources, as well as historiography and source studies of different periods in his work.

In his monograph "Empires of the Silk Road (a history of Central Eurasia from the Bronze age to the present)" Motherland is described as a region where the interests of Arabs, Turks, Chinese and Tibetans collide [16: 133].

European researchers were among the first to pay attention to the issue of Movarounnahr's occupation by the caliphate. For example, A.R. Gibb [20: 29-98] specifically focused on the military campaigns of the Arab caliphate and the activities of the anti-Arab coalition in Movarounnahr. RN Fry studied the caliphate policy in Movarounnahr based on numismatic materials [21: 34-41].

One of the first works in English about the Arab conquests in Central Asia is A. R. Gibb's study "The Arab conquests in Central Asia" [20]. The first draft of this work was submitted to the University of London in December 1921 as a thesis for the degree of Master of Arts under the title "The Arab Conquest of Transoxania" and approved by the Senate in January 1922. It does not claim to provide a complete historical account of the Arab invasion of Central Asia, but is intended only to provide a more detailed critical study than has been done so far. To reduce the

cost of publication, the extensive references originally included in the text have been reduced to a few notes at the end of each chapter. In most cases, it is easily found in the relevant place of Tabari or Balazuri, and no reference is given elsewhere. [20: 29-98].

Among the foreign researchers, the British Islamic scholar G.R. Hawting published his work on the dynastic significance of the Umayyad rule [22: 105-108]. English historian W. L. Novak on the anti-Umayyad group and opposition, in particular "foreigners" and Kharis ibn Surayj [23: 90-133], M.D. Luse about the tax policy carried out by the caliphate administration in Mowarounnahr [24: 34- 51], P.B.Golden [25: 160-166] cite the alliance of the oasis rulers and the Turks in Mowarounnahr against the forces of the Arab caliphate.

English historian W. L. Novak in his research entitled "The Delineation Between Believer, Rebel, and Heretic: Islamic Heterodoxy in the Late Umayyad Period" by studying two early Islamic heretics al-Harith ibn Surayj and Jahm ibn Safwan, Islam in the late Umayyad period. examines the concept of orthodoxy and heresy in its context. The influence of these movements on the national liberation movement in remote countries, the role of the caliphate and the decline of the Umayyad administration provide information about the condition of the heretics and their condemnation during this period. Using al-Tabari's Tarikh and al-Balazuri's Ansab al-Ashrof, the researcher sheds light on the difficult conditions of Islamic heterodoxy growing with the gradual codification of Islamic orthodoxy [23: 90-133].

Also, in the studies of Sharon Moshe [26: 261-323], A.H. Jangebe [28: 5], the political processes in Mowarounnahr were studied within the framework of the opposition against the Abbasids in the Arab caliphate. About the battle of Talas and the defeat of China in Mowarounnahr, B. Hoberman [29: 26-31], G.R. Hoyland [31: 148-151, 163-169, 181-195, 201-205], B. Jonathan [32: 42- 44] conducted research.

Hugh Kennedy, a British medieval historian, in his monograph "Velikie arabskie zavoevaniya" [30] ("The Great Conquests of the Arabs") mentions Qutayba ibn Muslim (86-96 / 705-715), Nasr ibn Sayyor (121-131 / 739-748) provides information about his military campaigns to Central Asia, including Fergana, the Battle of Talos (751) and their consequences. During the campaigns of Qutayba ibn Muslim, the resistance actions of Gurak, governor of Sughd, Divashtich, governor of Panjikent, and Alutar, ruler of Ferghana, are described. References are not made to the source of the information presented in the historical work. Nevertheless, we can conclude from the content of the information that he used only Arabic sources.

In the monograph "Imperial Chinese military history: 8000 BC - 1912 AD" [27] published by S. Whiting Marvin in New York in 2002, mutual relations between the Tang Empire and Ferghana state in the first half of the 8th century is told about. According to his work, Alutar came to the throne with the help of the Arabs in 715 [27: 276]. S. Whiting Marvin does not cite any works or sources in support of the information presented in his work. Therefore, his opinions are considered controversial.

Among the English-language studies created at the end of the 20th century, Khalid Yahya Blenkinship's work "The End of the Jihâd State: The Reign of Hisham Ibn Àbd AlMalik and the Collapse of the Umayyads" stands out. . In the work, the process called "Jihad State" in scientific literature, which began in 623 AD and continued until 750 AD, is a periodical sequence of Arab conquests, first local and then international, under the guise of Islamization [33: X]. A large-scale military campaign against Mowarounnahr occurs during the third expansion of the caliphate. In the years 73-99/692-718 we witness the conquest of North Africa, Spain, Mowarounnahr and Sindh. This time the Muslim expansion was stopped not by an internal conflict, but by an external defeat inflicted by the Byzantines in Constantinople in 98-99/717-18. The next hiatus in 99-101/718-20 was a voluntary cessation of hostilities by Caliph Umar II in view of this defeat [33: 19]. In the work, it is emphasized that Mowarounnahr is the front with the best information about the caliphate campaigns due to the fact that the Abbasids have preserved the traditions of the land on which their power was based. At the same time, the author

states that the relative abundance of information on military operations in Movarounnahr does not mean that this was the most dangerous front [33: 125].

Nevertheless, a serious test appeared for the Muslim troops led by Hisham on the Mowarounnahr front. During the reign of Yazid II, attempts to return the jizya to the new Muslims in Mowarounnahr angered the local population so much that some of them rebelled against the Muslim government. Although these were destroyed as a result of violent campaigns, the people of Movarounnahr also turn to Turkash Khan to protect themselves from the caliphate [33: 125-126].

In the work, a special place is devoted to the topic of the conflict between the Khagan of Turkash and the Umayyads. To the east of the Khazars, Muslims clashed with another Turkic state - the Turkash Khaganate. However, due to the lack of cities in the Turkic kingdom, it was considered a less settled state than the Khazar khanate, and its armies belonged to the typical Central Asian nomadic forces, highly mobile and without a clear target to defend. Although it is recognized in Chinese sources that there were two hundred to three hundred thousand warriors, this is a slight exaggeration, the strength of the Turgesh was more in mobility and fighting qualities than in numbers [33: 109]. Of course, the Movarounnahr people made good use of Umu-Turkish conflicts in the fight against the Arabs, and it was reflected in this work [33: 109].

The identity of Tarkhan Tirek/Nizak, who tried to oppose the Umayyad conquest of Central Asia in 709-710, has already been the subject of research, but most researchers believe that Tabari's contemporary Ibn Assam al-Kufi's *Kitab al-futuh* could not use the information provided in the Arabic manuscript. E. Esin's "Tarkhan Nīzak or Tarkhan Tirek?" An Inquiry concerning the Prince of Badhghīs Who in A. H. 91/A. D. 709-710 Opposed the 'Umayyad Conquest of Central Asia' article [34: 323-332] attempts to re-evaluate previous conclusions about Tarkhan Tirek/Nizak based on al-Kufi's comments. Several people, maybe two, held the title of Tarkhan Tirek/Nizak. According to the scientist, these were not Eftali princes, but Tarkhan tirek mansabdars who were vassals of the Turkish Yabgu in Tokharistan, were Turkic officials [34: 323].

One of the researchers who provided information about the activities of Nizak Tarkhan is Hudodad Rizakhoni. According to Hudodad Rizakhani's voluminous article *From the Kushans to the Western Turks*, a king named Khedzieji, who claimed to be the twelfth king of the dynasty ruling Jibin or Kabul according to the *Tangshu*, was independent of the Nezak Shahs until at least 661. carried out activities. The Nezak network that ruled over Zabulistan probably survived into the same period as the Late Nezak period before it was given over to Turkic rule. The local nature of the Nezak dynasty and their connection with the Alkhans meant that they remained local rulers under Turkic rule and even after the fall of Turkic power [36: 211].

The activity of Nizak Tarkhan, who was considered a descendant of the Ephthalites and played an important role in the fight against the Arabs, has been studied to a certain extent through Arab-Persian and Chinese sources. However, scientists have not yet been able to make a clear conclusion that Nizak Tarkhan was one or two people. Minoru Inaba is one of the scholars who researched the activities of Nizak Tarkhan through Chinese sources. In his article "Nezak in Chinese sources" M. Inaba systematizes and analyzes Chinese sources about his activity and origin [35: 191]. As a conclusion, M. Inaba states that Nizak Tarkhan may have been a local dynasty but was given the title of Hephthal [35: 200]. Of course, it is difficult to make a clear conclusion about the activity and origin of Nizak Tarkhan only through Chinese sources. Because the Arabic sources related to this matter are also important.

Soren Srak, who worked at New York University, wrote "The Arab Conquest of Bukhara: Reconsidering Qutayba b. In the article "Muslim's Campaigns 87–90 H/706–709 CE", Qutayba ibn Muslim's conquest activities, Arab campaigns in Bukhara are reviewed in the context of the historical topography of the region. He offers a new but more coherent reconstruction of the course of events during these marches. The resulting new article recounts how difficult the first

step in the conquest of Mowarounnahr was for the Arab forces and the struggle of local leaders against the Arabs.

Conclusion. The early medieval history of Central Asia, in particular, the subjugation of the region to the Arab caliphate, has been comprehensively studied and researched in English historiography. The work carried out by English Orientalists and English-language scholars, who are considered to be accomplished specialists in Oriental languages, play an important role in the study of the Arab conquests in Central Asia, since most of the research works and literature were written and published by them..

List of used sources and literature

1. Али-заде А.А. Хроники мусульманских государств I–VII веков хиджры. Изд. 2/е, испр. и доп. – Москва: Умма, 2004. – 445 с
2. Алмас Т. Уйгуры. Кн.2. – Алма-Ата, 1994. – 351 с.
3. Большаков О.Г. История Халифата. Т.IV. Апогей и падение. – Москва: Восточная литература РАН, 2010. – 369 с.
4. Брыкина Г.А., Горбунова Н.Г. Фергана / Средняя Азия и Дальний Восток в эпоху средневековья. Под общей редакцией академика Б.А.Рыбакова. – Москва: Наука, 1999. – 380 с.
5. Велльхаузен Ю. Арабский халифат. Золотой век ислама / Пер. с англ. Т.М.Шуликовой. – Москва: Центрполиграф, 2018. – 176 с.
6. Караев О.К. Арабские источники / Источниковедение Кыргызстана (с древности до конца XIX в.) – Бишкек: Илим, 2004. – 102 с.
7. Кеннеди Х. Великие арабские завоевания / Хью Кеннеди: пер. с англ. Г.Соловьевой. – Москва: АСТ, 2010. – 475 с.
8. Кожа М. Походы арабов в районы Ферганы, Чача и Средней Сырдарьи в VIII веке // Материалы и исследования по археологии Кыргызстана. Вып. 4. – Бишкек: Илим, 2009. – С. 97–103.
9. Курбанов А. Эфталиты (очерки истории). – Санкт-Петербург: Европейский дом, 2006. – 152 с.
10. Лившиц В. А. Согдийская эпиграфика Средней Азии и Семиречья. – Санкт-Петербург, 2008. – 238 с.
11. Роберт Ч. Истер. Буддизм. Путь к нирване. В кн. Религиозные традиции мира. – Бишкек, 1997. – 248 с.
12. Фильштинский И.М. Халифат под властью династии Омайядов (661–750). – Москва: Соверо-принт, 2005. – 232 с.
13. Фильштинский И.М. История арабов и халифата (750–1517). – Москва: Восток-Запад, 2006. – 350 с.
14. Bai Shouyi. A history of Chinese Muslim. Vol. 2. Beijing: Zhongua Book Company, 2002.
15. Christopher I. Beckwith. The Tibetan empire in Central Asia: a history of the struggle for great power among tibetians, Turks, Arabs and Chinese during the early middle ages. – New Jersey: Prinseton university press, 1993. – 281 p.
16. Christopher I. Beckwith. Empires of the Silk Road (a history of Central Eurasia from the Bronze age to the present). – New Jersey: Prinseton university press, 2009. – 499 p.
17. D`herbelot M.B. Bibliotheque oriental ov dictionaire universel. – Paris: Compagnie des Libra`res, 1777. – 1078 p.

18. Enoki K. On the Nationality of the Ephtalites // *Memoirs of the Research Department of the Toyo Bunko*, 1959. №18. – P. 1–59.
19. Enoki K. The origin of the white or Heptalites // *EW*. 1955. Vol. VI. – P. 232–236.
20. Gibb H.A.R. *The Arab conquests in Central Asia*. – London, 1923
21. Frye R.N. *Notes on the early coinage of Transoxania*. – New York, 1949
22. Hawting G.R. *The First Dynasty of Islam The Umayyad Caliphate (661-750)*. – New York: Taylor & Francis, 2002
23. Novak V.L. *The delineation between believer, rebel, and heretic: islamic heterodoxy in the late umayyad period*. – Maryland: Advisory Committee, 2012
24. Luce M.D. *Frontier as process: Umayyad Khurāsān*. – Chicago: Illinois, 2009
25. Golden P.B. *Türk halklari tarihine giriş / çeviren O. Karatay*. – Çorum, 2006
26. Moshe Sh. *Revolt: The Social and Military Aspects of the 'Abbāsīd revolution*. – Jerusalem: Graph Press, 1990
27. Marvin C Whiting. *Imperial Chinese military history: 8000 BC – 1912 AD*. New York: Writes club press, 2002
28. Jangebe H.A. Abu Muslim Al-Khurasani: The Legendary Hero of Abbasid Propaganda // *Journal of humanities and social science*. Volume 19, Issue 1, Ver. III, 2014
29. Hoberman B. The battle of Talas // *Saudi Aramco World*, September / October 1982
Hoyland R.G. *In God's Path: The Arab Conquests and the Creation of an Islamic Empire*. – New York: Oxford University Press, 2015
30. Кеннеди Х. Великие арабские завоевания / Хью Кеннеди; пер. с англ. Г. Соловьевой. – М.: АСТ, 2010
31. Hoyland R.G. *In God's Path: The Arab Conquests and the Creation of an Islamic Empire*. – New York: Oxford University Press, 2015
32. Jonathan B.M. *Paper Before Print: The History and Impact of Paper in the Islamic World*. – Singapore: CS Graphics, 2001
33. Blankinship, Khalid Yahya. *The End of the Jihād State : The Reign of Hisham Ibn Àbd AlMalik and the Collapse of the Umayyads* SUNY Series in Medieval Middle East History. State University of New York Press. 1994.
34. Inaba, Minoru "Nezak in Chinese Sources". *Coins, Art and Chronology II: The First Millennium C.E. in the Indo-Iranian Borderlands*. 2010. – P. 191-202.
35. Esin E. Tarkhan Nīzak or Tarkhan Tirek? An Enquiry concerning the Prince of Badhghīs Who in A. H. 91/A. D. 709-710 Opposed the 'Omayyad Conquest of Central Asia // *Journal of the American Oriental Society*, Vol. 97, No. 3 (Jul. - Sep., 1977), pp. 323- 332.
36. Rezakhani Kh. From the Kushans to the Western Turks. In *King of the Seven Climes. A History of the Ancient Iranian World (3000 BCE – 651 CE)*, (Ancient Iran Series 4), ed. T. Daryaee, 2017. 199–214.